

Peroxomonosulfuric acid oxidations : kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of cyclic ketones

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The kinetics of oxidation of cyclic ketones by peroxomonosulfuric acid (PMSA) have been studied in the pH range 0–9.65. The reaction follows second-order kinetics – first-order each in [PMSA] and [ketone] at constant pH. The observed pH-rate profile has been rationalised invoking HSO_5^- , SO_5^{2-} , the protonated and unprotonated forms of cyclic ketone as the reactive species, and their reactivities have been determined. The activation parameters of the reactions have been evaluated. A mechanism consistent with rate-determining nucleophilic attack of peroxo species on carbonyl-carbon of the neutral as well as protonated form of the cyclic ketone molecule has been proposed.

Baeyer-Villiger oxidation of alicyclic ketones to esters and cyclic ketones to lactone with peroxy acids have been extensively studied^{1,2} from the preparative, kinetics and mechanistic points of view.

The kinetics of reaction of alicyclic ketones with perbenzoic acid have been investigated by Friess^{3,4}, Mateos and Menchaca⁵. The relative rates of oxidation of different cyclic ketones, as well as the mechanism of the ring expansion involved in lactone formation have been discussed.

Panigrahi *et al.*⁶ studied the oxidation of cyclopentanone, cyclohexanone and cyclooctanone by peroxomonophosphoric acid (PMPA) in the pH range 0–3; a cyclic transition state for the reaction was proposed. H_3PO_5 has been reported to be the only reactive species of PMPA in the oxidation. The reactivity of H_2PO_5^- in the reaction was ruled out basing on the assumption that with H_2PO_5^- species it was difficult to visualise a cyclic transition state of the type proposed for the reaction.

The present paper deals with the kinetics of oxidation of cyclic ketones by peroxomonosulfuric acid in the pH range 0–9.65. The relative reactivities of HSO_5^- and SO_5^{2-} in the oxidation have been discussed. The pH-rate profile in the present investigation is found to be totally different from that observed in PMPA-cyclic ketone reaction⁶.

Results and discussion

The kinetics of oxidation of cyclic ketones by peroxomonosulfuric acid have been investigated at 308 K. The reactions at constant pH and ionic strength, μ , were found to be independent of the initial PMSA concentra-

tion. This indicates that the reaction is first-order with respect to PMSA. The rates of oxidation of both the substrates were measured at various initial concentration of substrate and are collected in Table 1. The plots of k'_1 vs [substrate]_t were found to be linear ($\gamma = 0.999$ for both cyclohexanone and cyclopentanone), and to pass through the origin showing that the reactions are also first-order with respect to substrate.

The variation of ionic strength using NaClO_4 was found to have negligible effect on oxidation rate. Addition of acrylamide also had no effect on the rate of oxidation. The rate of oxidation is found to decrease with an increase in the acetonitrile content in the solvent mixture (Table 1). This may be due to the decrease in polarity of the reaction medium.

The reactions have been studied at different temperatures in the range 308–328 K, and the rate constants are presented in Table 2. From the linear Arrhenius plots of $\log k'_2$ vs T^{-1} ($\gamma = 0.996$ and 0.997 for cyclopentanone and cyclohexanone respectively), the activation parameters ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger have been calculated to be 48 kJ mol^{-1} and $-134 \pm 1 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ for cyclopentanone, and 38 kJ mol^{-1} and $-147 \pm 1 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ for cyclohexanone.

The oxidation of cyclopentanone and cyclohexanone by PMSA has been studied at different pH in the pH ranges 0–9.4 and 0–9.65 respectively. The rate data are summarised in Table 3, and plots of $\log k'_2$ vs pH are shown in Fig. 1.

The pH-rate profiles in both the cases are found to be V-shaped with the rate minimum at $\text{pH} \approx 3.50$. These obser-

Table 1. Second-order rate constants for the oxidation of cyclic ketones by peroxomonosulfuric acid

Temp. = 308 K, aqueous medium, $[H^+] = 0.25 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

Substrate (S)	$10^2 [S]_t$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^4 [PMSA]_t$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^4 k'_1$ s ⁻¹	$10^2 k'_2$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
Cyclopentanone	2.23	5.43	1.04	0.467
	4.55	5.89	2.06	0.453
	9.09	4.54	3.94	0.433
	18.2	5.89	8.63	0.473
	4.50	5.91	2.09	0.464 ^a
	9.21	1.95	4.01	0.433
	9.03	6.08	3.62	0.401
	9.03	8.98	4.22	0.467
	9.21	4.08	3.72	0.404 ^b
	3.22	3.56	0.96	0.300 ^c
Cyclohexanone	0.233	4.29	1.01	4.33
	0.460	4.25	1.96	4.25
	1.15	4.33	4.91	4.25
	2.03	4.01	8.60	4.24
	2.07	2.21	8.12	3.92
	2.07	5.88	8.16	3.94
	2.07	8.51	8.46	4.08
	2.25	4.54	9.41	4.18 ^d
	2.02	3.72	7.32	3.62 ^e
	2.39	4.05	3.82	1.59 ^f
2.09	3.97	2.43	1.16 ^g	

^a[Acrylamide] = $4.48 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, ^b $\mu = 0.75 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, ^cacetonitrile : water = 40 : 60 (v/v), ^d $\mu = 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, ^eacetonitrile : water = 10 : 90 (v/v), ^facetonitrile : water = 20 : 80 (v/v), ^gacetonitrile : water = 40 : 60 (v/v).

Table 2. Effect of temperature on second-order rate constants in the oxidation of cyclic ketones by peroxomonosulfuric acid

$[H^+] = 0.25 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, aqueous medium

Substrate (S)	Temperature (K)	$10^2 k'_2$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
Cyclopentanone ^a	308	0.429
	313	0.657
	318	0.842
	328	1.48
Cyclohexanone ^b	308	4.25
	313	5.89
	318	7.17
	328	11.5

^a $[PMSA]_t = (4.4-4.7) \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[cyclopentanone]_t = (9.03-9.14) \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, ^b $[PMSA]_t = (4.3-4.7) \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[cyclohexanone]_t = (1.15-1.88) \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Table 3. Oxidation of cyclic ketones by peroxomonosulfuric acid at different pH

Temp. = 308 K, aqueous medium

Substrate (S)	pH	$10^2 k'_2$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	$10^2 k'_2$ (calcd.) dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
Cyclopentanone ^a	0	1.13	1.16
	0.30	0.615	0.657
	0.60	0.433	0.404
	1.00	0.263	0.252
	2.06	0.158	0.159
	3.25	0.043	0.151
	4.25	0.121	0.151
	5.25	0.344	0.155
	6.58	1.79	0.226
	7.71	2.73	1.37
	8.10	3.73	3.12
	8.92	12.8	15.0
	9.40	29.2	31.1
	Cyclohexanone ^b	0	6.15
0.30		5.34	4.95
0.60		4.24	4.24
1.00		4.09	3.81
2.00		1.61	3.55
3.5		0.45	3.52
4.52		1.23	3.53
5.31		3.78	3.56
5.55		4.66	3.60
6.68		6.58	5.04
7.10		7.23	5.56
7.60		11.6	9.90
8.49		47.7	48.2
8.91		99.2	101
9.23	166	167	
9.47	228	223	
9.65	234	264	

^a $[PMSA]_t = (1.73-6.08) \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[cyclopentanone]_t = (0.89-9.21) \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, ^b $[PMSA]_t = (2.22-5.41) \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[cyclohexanone]_t = (0.13-2.57) \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

variations seem to be totally different when compared with the observations made in the oxidation of cyclic ketones by peroxomonophosphoric acid⁶. In the oxidation of cyclohexanone, 2-methyl cyclohexanone and 2-hydroxy cyclohexanone by PMPA⁶, the rate of reaction increased exponentially with increasing $[H^+]$ upto $[H^+] \approx 0.35 \text{ M}$ and then became almost independent of $[H^+]$. No reaction was observed at $\text{pH} > 3$.

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log k_2$ vs pH : (A) PMSA ~ cyclopentanone, (B) PMSA ~ cyclohexanone.

The acid catalysis in the reaction of carbonyl compounds are normally traced to the protonation of the carbonyl group⁷.

In the oxidation of benzil⁸, 1,4-cyclohexanedione⁹ and aliphatic aldehydes¹⁰ in acid medium with different peroxy acids, participation of both the neutral as well as protonated forms of the substrate has been reported. The reaction of benzalacetone¹¹, an α,β -unsaturated ketone, with peracetic acid has also been reported to involve protonation of the >C=O group.

In the present study, the acid catalysis in the pH regions 0–3.25 and 0–3.5 for cyclopentanone and cyclohexanone oxidation respectively, could be explained by assuming the participation of both the neutral as well as protonated forms of the ketone molecule in the reaction.

Rate law and mechanism :

In the pH range studied both cyclopentanone and cyclohexanone exist in neutral (S) as well as in protonated (SH^+) form.

where $K_1 = 3.16 \times 10^{-8}$ and 1.58×10^{-7} for cyclopentanone and cyclohexanone respectively⁷.

In peroxomonosulfuric acid¹² ($\text{HO-SO}_3\text{H}$) one proton is a sulfuric acid proton and the other a hydrogen peroxide proton. The $\text{p}K_2$ value of sulfuric acid proton lies in the high acidity region while the hydrogen peroxide proton has a $\text{p}K_2$ value of 9.4, thus indicating that in the pH range stud-

ied PMSA exists as HSO_5^- and SO_5^{2-} .

The various steps involved in the oxidation of cyclic ketones by PMSA in the explored range of pH can be explained by a mechanism in which the protonated and neutral forms of the cyclic ketone molecule react simultaneously with HSO_5^- and SO_5^{2-} in parallel reactions.

The rate law pertaining to these reaction steps are

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= \frac{-d[\text{PMSA}]_t}{dt} \\ &= k_1 [\text{HSO}_5^-] [\text{S}] + k_2 [\text{HSO}_5^-] [\text{SH}^+] \\ &\quad + k_3 [\text{SO}_5^{2-}] [\text{S}] + k_4 [\text{SO}_5^{2-}] [\text{SH}^+] \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where, $[\text{PMSA}]_t$ represents the total analytical concentration of PMSA and is expressed as

$$[\text{PMSA}]_t = [\text{HSO}_5^-] + [\text{SO}_5^{2-}] \quad (9)$$

The total analytical concentration of cyclic ketone is given in eq. (10).

$$[\text{S}]_t = [\text{S}] + [\text{SH}^+] \quad (10)$$

From eqs. (3) and (9), we have

$$[\text{HSO}_5^-] = \frac{[\text{PMSA}]_t [\text{H}^+]}{K_2 + [\text{H}^+]} \quad (11)$$

and

$$[\text{SO}_5^{2-}] = \frac{K_2 [\text{PMSA}]_t}{K_2 + [\text{H}^+]} \quad (12)$$

From eqs. (2) and (10), we have

$$[\text{S}] = [\text{S}]_t \left\{ \frac{1}{1 + K_1 [\text{H}^+]} \right\} \quad (13)$$

$$[\text{SH}^+] = [\text{S}]_t \left\{ \frac{K_1[\text{H}^+]}{1 + K_1[\text{H}^+]} \right\} \quad (14)$$

Substituting eqs. (11), (12), (13) and (14) in eq. (8), we get

$$\frac{-d[\text{PMSA}]_t}{dt} = \frac{\left\{ \frac{k_1[\text{H}^+] + k_2K_1[\text{H}^+]^2 + k_3K_2 + k_4K_1K_2[\text{H}^+]}{(K_2 + [\text{H}^+])(1 + K_1[\text{H}^+])} \right\} [\text{PMSA}]_t [\text{S}]_t}{(14)}$$

or

$$k'_2 = \left\{ \frac{k_1[\text{H}^+] + k_2K_1[\text{H}^+]^2 + k_3K_2 + k_4K_1K_2[\text{H}^+]}{(K_2 + [\text{H}^+])(1 + K_1[\text{H}^+])} \right\} \quad (16)$$

The average values of k_1 , k_2 , k_3 and k_4 , obtained by least-squares analysis¹³ of the data according to eq. (16) for the oxidation of both cyclopentanone and cyclohexanone are presented in Table 4. These values have been used to calculate k'_2 (calcd) in Table 3.

Table 4. Average values of computed rate constants for the oxidation of cyclopentanone and cyclohexanone by PMSA at 35°C^a

Reaction	Computed rate constant/dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	
	Cyclopentanone	Cyclohexanone
HSO ₅ ⁻ ~ S (k_1)	0.12 × 10 ⁻²	2.90 × 10 ⁻²
HSO ₅ ⁻ ~ SH ⁺ (k_2)	3.20 × 10 ⁵	1.80 × 10 ⁵
SO ₅ ²⁻ ~ S (k_3)	0.62	4.10
SO ₅ ²⁻ ~ SH ⁺ (k_4)	2.42 × 10 ¹³	9.90 × 10 ¹³

^aAqueous medium.

The nucleophilic behaviour of peroxy anion, in the reactions of carbonyl compounds with peroxy acids has been well established⁷. These reactions usually take place by a nucleophilic attack of the peroxide molecule on the carbonyl group forming a peroxy-intermediate, which in a subsequent step undergoes oxygen-oxygen bond fission resulting in carbon to oxygen migrations.

In the oxidation⁶ of cyclic ketones by PMPA, the reaction has been shown to proceed through a cyclic transition state involving only H₃PO₅. The lack of reactivity of H₂PO₅⁻ in the reaction has been explained on the basis that a cyclic transition state of the type proposed can not be visualised with H₂PO₅⁻ species. In the present study, however, both HSO₅⁻ and SO₅²⁻ are found to be reactive. The non-exist-

ence of H₂SO₅ species in the reaction system in the range of pH studied, and the reactivity order SO₅²⁻ > HSO₅⁻ do not favour the reaction to proceed through a cyclic transition state as has been proposed in case of PMPA – cyclic ketone reaction.

The oxidation of cyclic ketones by PMSA is proposed to involve a rate-determining nucleophilic attack of the peroxy species on the carbonyl-carbon of both the protonated and unprotonated ketone in the pH range 0–3.5, and of unprotonated ketone in the pH ranges 3.5–9.4 and 3.5–9.65 respectively for cyclopentanone and cyclohexanone. The reactivity order (Table 4) SO₅²⁻ > HSO₅⁻ is in quite agreement with the nucleophilic participation of PMSA in the reaction^{10,14}. The higher reactivity of protonated ketone as compared to neutral one, with any particular PMSA species, also parallels the increased electrophilic character of the carbonyl carbon in the protonated ketone⁸.

Scheme 1

The higher reactivity of cyclohexanone, the six membered ketone, as compared to that observed for cyclopentanone or cycloheptanone is in accord with the concept of Brown¹⁵, relating to I-strain as the determining factor in the rates of addition reactions to carbonyl group contained in common-sized rings.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical grade. Conductivity water was used in the preparation of the solutions and as a reaction medium. The potassium salt of Caro's acid, oxone (2KHSO₅·KHSO₄·K₂SO₄) (Dupont), was used to prepare PMSA solutions. Cyclohexanone, cyclopentanone (B.D.H.) were distilled before use. The ionic strength of the medium was maintained with sodium perchlorate which was prepared *in situ* by neutralizing perchloric acid with carbonate-free sodium hydroxide. Acidity of the solutions was maintained by adding calculated amounts of HClO₄ or standard buffers such as acetic acid-sodium acetate, sodium hydroxide-potassium hydrogen

phthalate, KH_2PO_4 - Na_2HPO_4 , Na_2CO_3 - NaHCO_3 . Measurements of pH were made on a Systronic digital pH meter 335. For experiments employing $[\text{H}^+] \geq 0.01 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, the $[\text{H}^+]$ was titrimetrically determined, and the pH values reported in the range 0–1 refer to the converted values from the measured $[\text{H}^+]$ concentrations.

The kinetics was followed by measuring rate of disappearance of peroxy acid, the estimation of which was made iodometrically using standard thiosulphate. The observed second-order rate constants ($k'_{2(\text{obs})}$) was calculated by dividing pseudo first-order rate constant (k'_1) with respect to peroxy acid disappearance by $[\text{ketone}]$. The rate constants were reproducible to $\pm 5\%$. The self decomposition of PMSA was found to be either nil or negligibly small under our experimental conditions. The temperature was constant to within $\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$.

Stoichiometry and product :

The stoichiometry of the PMSA-cyclohexanone reaction with excess of PMSA over cyclohexanone was determined by estimating the left over [PMSA], when the reaction was complete ($\text{PMSA} = 11.9 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, cyclohexanone = $4.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{H}^+] = 0.25 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, 35°C). The PMSA : cyclohexanone ratio for the reaction was found to be 1 : 1. The overall reaction can hence be presented as

In the oxidation of cyclanones by different peracids^{3,4}, the corresponding lactone has been identified as product.

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